

SURROGATE MODELING APPROACH FOR STATISTICAL SIMULATION OF LINEAR CAR SUSPENSION DYNAMICS

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d.yuldashev@polito.uz**Abstract** — A parametric uncertainty analysis of a car suspension system was conducted in this study. Four degrees-of-freedom (DOF) mathematical models were developed for both passive and semi-active suspension systems, and the uncertainty of these models was analyzed using a surrogate modeling approach. This approach employed polynomial-based surrogate models to simulate uncertainties, offering an alternative to traditional Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. The results indicate that the surrogate modeling method is not only more computationally efficient but also robust in capturing the uncertainty in dynamic systems compared to the MC approach, making it a powerful tool for the statistical simulation of linear car suspension dynamics.

Keywords – surrogate modeling, linear car suspension dynamics, uncertainty analysis, polynomial-based surrogate model, Monte Carlo method

Introduction

Although criteria in automotive engineering are generally considered deterministic, numerous uncertainties can significantly impact a vehicle's dynamic performance. Factors such as manufacturing imperfections, mechanical wear, and variability in material properties introduce these uncertainties. Traditional deterministic methods may yield acceptable results when parameter variations are small. However, as the number of uncertain parameters grows or the range of variability becomes substantial, deterministic approaches may fail to provide accurate predictions [1].

Recently, Monte Carlo simulations and polynomial-based surrogate modeling techniques have been employed in various applications to address uncertainty quantification challenges. This study proposes the use of a surrogate modeling

approach, leveraging polynomial-based surrogate models, to estimate system dynamics under uncertainty. This method offers a computationally efficient alternative to traditional Monte Carlo approaches, particularly for complex systems with high degrees of uncertainty in key parameters.

The surrogate modeling approach has shown effectiveness in a variety of applications, including the prediction of vehicle dynamics. In this study, we apply this technique to a four-degree-of-freedom linear suspension system model for a half-car configuration, providing a robust framework for simulating uncertainty in linear car suspension dynamics [2].

We swiftly examine PC expansion and its mathematical definitions in Chapter 2, following the introduction. Next, we discuss how well PC expansion performs in comparison to MC and provide instances in chapters 3 and 4. The final section of the paper presents the conclusions derived from the simulations.

Polynomial chaos expansion

2.1. Polynomial chaos expansion

The polynomial chaos expansion is used to represent a stochastic process of polynomial functions of uncertainty dynamic system in this section. We also show how to build model of the system using this approach [5].

Let us take the following actual parametric system into consideration:

$$Y = M(X) \quad (1)$$

where $Y \in \mathbb{R}$ is the output of the system and $X = \{ X_i, i = 1, \dots, N \}$ is a vector which captures the parameters of the system. The aim is to construct a compact and precise mathematical representation \tilde{M} is the so called surrogate model of the system M .

Polynomial Chaos expansions of stochastic processes:

$$Y \approx \tilde{M}_{PC}(X) = \sum_{k=0}^k a_k \psi_k(X) \quad (2)$$

Y is the random response and X is the random variables of a mechanical model.

$$K + 1 = \frac{(p + n)!}{p!n!}$$

, n is the number of random variables and p is the maximum order of the polynomial basis.

a_k are coefficients to be computed (coordinates)

$\psi_k(X)$ is an orthonormal basis [4]

Mathematical formulation of car suspension system

To reduce vibrations that are distributed from the ground surface to the car body, the car suspension system has been used. A soft suspension is needed for good riding convenience and a hard suspension is needed to handle higher weight. An active suspension system is preferred over a simple passive suspension system to satisfy these two concepts were mentioned in the above. In optimizing both ride comfort and road holding that active suspensions are getting more interest. Active suspension provides a desirable performance improved by an active suspension without costly hardware [13]. So, the most frequently used in specific applications are active and prototypes.

The mathematical representation of the suspension system for cars is discussed in this section. We can be used the passive suspension system of half car model as linear case [12].

First, the model of passive suspension was shown in Fig.1.

FIGURE 1

Half car representation of passive suspension system

Mathematical equations that describe the suspension system should first be formulated in order to simulate the suspension system. For this reason, the basic theory of dynamics was adopted to the suspension system. Few basic assumptions were considered for mathematical relations for sprung and unsprung masses.

There are some assumptions such as car does not leave the ground, velocity of the car is constant and sprung mass is considered to be uniformly distributed and also pitch angle is given very small [11].

In Fig.1, where the spring mass is described by m_s , and the unsprung mass of the front and rear suspension is described by m_{u1} , m_{u2} respectively, and the springs of stiffness of front and rear suspension is described by k_{s1} , k_{s2} respectively and the dampers with damping coefficient of front and rear suspension is described by c_{s1} , c_{s2} respectively.

z_{si} , z_{ui} ($i=1,2$) are the vertical displacements of the sprung and unsprung mass of front and rear suspension respectively. z_{ri} ($i=1,2$) is vertical displacement from road surface and z_c is the car (body) displacement. The corresponding stiffness of the front and rear tires is k_{t1} , k_{t2} . l_f , l_r is the length between the center of gravity and the front axle or the rear axle. The moment of inertia is I_0 [10].

It is possible to write z_{ri} ($i=1,2$) as:

$$z_{s1} = z_c + l_f \theta \quad (7)$$

$$z_{s2} = z_c + l_r \theta \quad (8)$$

The basic form of the State-space model is used to model the suspension system:

$$\dot{q} = Aq + Bu$$

$$y = Cq + Du$$

The model of state space can be given by the following:

$$q = \begin{bmatrix} z_c \\ \theta \\ z_{u1} \\ z_{u2} \\ \cdot \\ z_c \\ \cdot \\ \theta \\ \cdot \\ z_{u1} \\ \cdot \\ z_{u2} \end{bmatrix} \quad u = \begin{bmatrix} z_{r1} \\ z_{r2} \end{bmatrix} \quad y = \begin{bmatrix} z_c \\ \theta \\ z_{u1} \\ z_{u2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Simulation results

The application of PC techniques to the half-car suspension is addressed in this chapter, which are already demonstrated in Fig. 1.

The passive suspension system has no external force, and the damping coefficient is not variable. Energy is dissipated while using damper and spring in that system. MATLAB/SIMULINK was used to do all the simulations. The simulink model is a bunch of different simulink blocks which are connected by arrows according to mathematical relations [11]. Passive suspension system of half car model is used to illustrate our linear case. Values of masses, damping coefficients and spring constants of sprung and unsprung masses on both front and rear wheels are taken into consideration for simulation.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF CAR

Parameters	Values
sprung mass (m_s)	800 kg
body mass moment of inertia (I_0)	3000 $m \times kg^2$

front and rear	35 kg
unsprung mass (m_{u1} and m_{u2})	
front and rear	24000
suspension stiffness (k_{s1} and k_{s2})	N / m
front and rear	2500
suspension damping (c_{s1} and c_{s2})	Ns / m
front and rear tyre	18000
stiffness (k_{t1} and k_{t2})	$0 N / m$
Location of center of gravity from front axle (l_f)	1.5 m
Location of center of gravity from rear axle (l_r)	1 m

The road input is the random road profile of ISO 8608. In accordance with ISO 8608 standard, it is possible to simulate external excitation of the suspension system in the form of a random road profile. z_r excitation from the road surface of the half car system is expressed by means of $z_r = 2\pi\sqrt{G_0V}\omega$, and where G_0 is the road roughness coefficient; V is the speed of the car; $\omega = [\omega_1, \omega_2]^T$ is Zero mean Gaussian white noise [17].

FIGURE 4

SIMULINK MODEL FOR PASSIVE SUSPENSION SYSTEM OF HALF CAR

We refer to the equivalent stiffness of the tire k_{t1}, k_{t2} as uncertainty parameters in order to provide a clear analysis of the problem.

$$k_{t1} = \bar{k}_{t1} + k'_{t1}\zeta_1 \tag{12}$$

$$k_{t2} = \bar{k}_{t2} + k'_{t2}\zeta_2 \tag{13}$$

The $x = [\zeta_1, \zeta_2]$ parameters are uniformly distributed in $X = [-1, 1]^2$. A uniform variation of $\pm 50\%$ around its central value is shown each parameter. The model of the system is the following

$$y(f; x) = M(f; x) \tag{14}$$

Figure 5 indicates the significant function distribution (14) resulting from the large uncertainty of the two stochastic parameters and obtained by MC simulation in the $f \in [0Hz; 10Hz]$ frequency range [9].

In (14) for the prediction of the probability density function of y, the surrogate model is used. The MC realizations were used in order to train the PC surrogate model, denoted as $\tilde{M}_{PC}(f; x)$ and that model is built by using Legendre polynomials due to the uniform distribution of the parameters.

The maximum total degree is $p = 6$. The model is estimated from a randomly selected range of $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^L$ samples. For a given size L, ten major realizations of the training set are considered.

Figure 6 contrasts the y PDF collected from 10000 MC (14) (solid black line) assessments with those calculated from the surrogate model trained with $L = 20, 30$ and 40 samples (dashed lines). As a consequence of the ten different realizations of the training set, the two lines represent the minimum and maximum value of the PDF. The model parameters are computed in the case of PC expansion by the solution of a least-square problem, which provides better results for overdetermined systems, as discussed in chapter 2.

According to chapter 2, for a PC expansion of order $p = 6$ and $n = 2$ random parameters, the number of PC expansion coefficients is 28. Next, the surrogate models are used to measure the PDF of the transfer function (14) at $f_0 = 0.3\text{Hz}$ frequencies, shown by the dashed vertical lines in Fig. 5. [8].

FIGURE 5

CAR BODY DISPLACEMENT AS LINEAR CASE

We can see that linear dynamic systems not to take too much time for simulation. It turns out that the suggested approach is more effective than traditional methods like MC.

FIGURE 6

PDF OF THE FUNCTION FIG. 5. THE RESULT COMPUTED FROM 10000 MC SAMPLES (SOLID BLACK CURVES) IS COMPARED WITH THE PREDICTIONS ACHIEVED VIA THE PC EXPANSION (DASHED GREEN CURVES). THE THREE PANELS CORRESPOND TO DIFFERENT TRAINING SET SIZES

Conclusion

This research investigates a practical method for starting with a small number of response samples and building a system surrogate model that focuses on highly variable parameters. A detailed overview of the polynomial chaos approach is presented for addressing uncertainties in linear, passive vehicle suspension systems. The researchers concluded that the polynomial chaos (PC) technique is a powerful approach for uncertainty quantification in parametric modeling of dynamic system simulations, proving to be more efficient than the Monte Carlo (MC) simulation method.

In an industrial setting, Monte Carlo techniques are often impractical due to their long computation times. In contrast, the PC approach is faster and significantly reduces computational costs. For example, the simulation of a linear, passive suspension system in a half-car model takes less than half an hour using the PC method, whereas Monte Carlo simulation would require much longer for comparable

accuracy. The PC approach can achieve accurate results with a smaller training set, making it especially beneficial for linear systems. This method provides robust and efficient modeling for such systems, producing accurate results while keeping computational demands low.

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